

Research Article

Analysis of dielectric constants and optical Properties of Magnesium: Beam Propagation Approach.

¹Ugwu Emmanuel. I*, ²Eke Vincent O.C and ²Elechi Onyekachi

¹Department of Industrial Physics, ²Department of Computer Science
Ebonyi State University, P.M.B 53 Abakaliki, Nigeria.

*Corresponding Author's Email: ugwuei@yahoo.com

Abstract

Beam propagation approach has been used to study the optical properties of magnesium. Maxwell's equations that relate electromagnetic wave propagation through material medium were derived and the reflection behaviour of the wave propagating through the medium is observed with regard to the influence of the refractive index and extinction coefficient. The damping effects on the propagating wave due to the influence of these properties were highlighted. The polarizability effect on the crystal lattice that resulted on the real and complex conductivity in relation to the skin depth coupled with the plasma frequency edge during which n and k are zero which is a factor that influences the reflection coefficient was presented.

Keyword: Maxwell's equation, refractive index, electromagnetic wave, dielectric constant, conductivity, polarizability, beam propagation extinction coefficient, Reflection coefficient.

1. Introduction

Many methods have been employed in studying optical property of materials such as beam propagation method in which computation technique is applied to beam or field propagating in a medium with variation of small refractive index [2] and [1][3] in order to ascertain its response to the propagated field. Some researchers had employed beam propagation method based on diagonalization of the Hermitian operator that generates the solution of the Helmholtz equation in media with real refractive indices[4][15] while some had used 2x2 propagation matrix formalism for finding the obliquely propagated electromagnetic fields in layered inhomogeneous un-axial structure[5,16]for the same purpose. While recently, we have looked at the propagation of electromagnetic field through a conducting surface [6,16] and we observed the behaviour of such a material. The effect of variation of refractive index of F_eS_2 had also been carried out [3]. The dielectric constants were obtained from a computation using pseudo-dielectric function in conjunction with experimentally measured extinction co-efficient [14] and the refractive indices of the film and the thickness of the film which was assumed to range from $0.1\mu\text{m}$ to $0.7\mu\text{m}$ [100nm to 500nm] based on the experimentally measured value, at the wavelength, $450\mu\text{m}$ have been studied [12][15]. This work is based on a method of using Maxwell's equation in conjunction with solid state properties of the material such as dielectric constant and refractive index to study the optical characteristic of magnesium using wave with time variation $e^{i\omega t}$ travelling in the z-direction with E and H parallel to x-and y- directions. With this technique the solution for n and k which represent refractive index and extinction coefficient that are real in nature and govern the damping of the wave in the material medium are obtained and that enabled us to analyze the response of the propagating field to the solid state properties of magnesium.

2. Theoretical Framework

[a] Formulation of wave equation involving dielectric constant

We begin with Maxwell's equations that relate electromagnetic wave propagation through material medium and the solid property of the material.

$$\text{CurlH} = \frac{4\pi j}{c} + \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial D}{\partial t} \quad [1]$$

$$\text{divD} = 4\pi j \quad [2]$$

$$\text{CurlE} = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial B}{\partial t} \quad [3]$$

where $D = \epsilon E$ and $B = \mu H$

ϵ and μ are the dielectric constant and permeability while j is the current due to the conduction electrons. The permeability is assumed to be unity.

Conversely, since $D = E + 4\pi\rho$, ρ now is considered to result from charge density ρ' given by

$$\text{div}\rho = \rho' \quad [4]$$

Associated with j' the current density that exists in parallel with the current density due to conduction electrons j given by

$$-\text{div}j' = \frac{\partial \rho'}{\partial t} \quad [5]$$

From equations 4 and 5, we can write

$$j' = \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} \quad [6]$$

Equation [6] represents the additional current [known as bound current] in conjunction to the current associated with the conduction electrons.

Conversely, we consider j to be absorbed into $\frac{\partial D}{\partial t}$, as we regard the entire solid as the medium through which electromagnetic wave propagates. For consistency, we take $j=0$ in equation [1 and 2] obtaining

$$\text{CurlH} = \frac{\epsilon}{c} \frac{\partial E}{\partial t} \quad \text{and} \quad \text{CurlE} = \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} \quad [7]$$

For wave with time variation $e^{i\omega t}$ travelling in the z -direction with E and H parallel to x - and y - directions respectively, we have

$$\frac{\partial H_y}{\partial z} = \frac{i\omega\epsilon E_x}{c} \quad [8]$$

$$\frac{\partial E_x}{\partial z} = \frac{i\omega}{c} H_y \quad [9]$$

Equations [8 and 9] enable us to obtain

$$\frac{\partial^2 E_x}{\partial z^2} = \frac{\omega^2 \epsilon}{c^2} E_x \quad [10]$$

whose solution is given as

$$E = E_o \exp i\omega \left[t - \frac{\mu z}{c} \right] \quad [11]$$

where $\mu = \sqrt{\epsilon}$

one can write equation [11] thus

$$E = E_o \exp i\omega \left(t - \frac{nz}{c} \right) \exp \left(\frac{-\omega kz}{c} \right) \quad [12]$$

[b] Influence of Solid state characteristic of magnesium on wave propagating through it

When wave propagates through a material, the solid state parameters such as n and k representing refractive index and extinction coefficient are real in nature and contribute to the damping of the wave propagating through the material medium as the relate to the dielectric constant.

Comparing equations [11 and 12], we have the relation such as

$$\sqrt{\epsilon} = \mu = n + ik \quad [13]$$

where

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_r + i\epsilon_i \quad [14]$$

Equations [13 and 14] can be written in terms of real and complex parts respectively as

$$\epsilon_r = n^2 - k^2 \quad [15]$$

and

$$\epsilon_i = 2nk \quad [16]$$

For normal incidence of the propagating wave, the reflection coefficient is given as

$$R = \left| \frac{\mu - 1}{\mu + 1} \right|^2 = \frac{(n-1)^2 + k^2}{(n+1)^2 + k^2} \quad [17]$$

[c] Effect of polarizability on Propagating Wave

On the account that wave propagating through a metal induces polarization on the lattice, we have

$$\text{Curl}E = \frac{4\pi j}{c} + \frac{\partial E}{\partial t} \quad [18]$$

of which with the time independent electric field $e^{i\omega t}$, we can write

$$j\sigma(\omega)E \quad [19]$$

that enabled us to obtain

$$\text{Curl}H = \left[\frac{4\pi}{c} \sigma(\omega) + \frac{i\omega}{c} \right] E \quad [20]$$

Comparing equation [20] with equation [3] we see that

$$\varepsilon(\omega) = 1 + \frac{4\pi i}{\omega} \sigma(\omega) \quad [21]$$

Since equation [21] refers only to the conduction electrons excluding the conductivity due to bound electrons, the medium in question here appears to be restricted to the free space. With the fact that we are not limited to only the free space, we can write

$$\varepsilon(\omega) = \varepsilon^o(\omega) + \frac{4\pi i}{\omega} \sigma(\omega) \quad [22]$$

Neglecting the polarizability, of the material, and relating it to the solid state property,

$$n^2 + k^2 = 1 + \frac{4\pi}{\omega} \sigma_r \quad [23]$$

$$nk = \frac{2\pi}{\omega} \sigma_i \quad [24]$$

where $\sigma_i = \frac{\sigma_o}{1 + \omega^2 \tau^2}$ and $\sigma_r = \frac{\omega_p \sigma_o}{1 + \omega^2 \tau^2}$ signify real and complex conductivity of the metal respectively.

Equation [23 and 24] can be transformed as

$$n^2 - k^2 = \frac{1 - \omega_p^2 \tau^2}{1 + \omega^2 \tau^2} \quad [25]$$

$$2nk = \frac{\omega_p^2 \tau^2}{\omega [1 + \omega^2 \tau^2]} \quad [26]$$

Considering the low frequency range of the electromagnetic wave where $\omega \tau \ll 1$, we observe that

$$(n + k)(n - k) \simeq 1 - \omega_p^2 \tau^2 \quad [27]$$

$$2nk \simeq \frac{\omega_p^2 \tau^2}{\omega} \quad [28]$$

From equation [28], it implies that n and k increase infinitely as $\omega \rightarrow 0$ while in equation [27],

$1 - \omega_p^2 \tau^2$ is independent of ω , then at this point the two optical constants become approximately equal. Thus we write

$$n \simeq k \simeq \sqrt{\frac{\omega_p^2 \tau^2}{2\omega}} = \sqrt{\frac{2\pi\sigma_o}{\omega}} \quad [29]$$

At this region, we obtain the distant at which the incident electromagnetic wave is attenuated to $\frac{1}{e}$ times its original value which from equation [14] is related to k by

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{c^2}{2\pi\sigma_o\omega}} \quad [30]$$

Within the range of the relaxation region where $\omega_\tau \gg 1$ which is the region of interest, we have

$$\epsilon_r = n^2 - k^2 \simeq 1 - \left[\frac{\omega_p}{\omega} \right]^2 \quad [31]$$

and

$$\epsilon_i = 2nk \simeq \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega_\tau^2} \quad [32]$$

However at the plasma edge, $\omega = \omega_p$ where we now have

$$n^2 - k^2 = 0, \text{ and } 2nk = \frac{1}{\omega_\tau} \ll 1 \quad [33]$$

At this time, n and k are zero thereby reducing the reflection coefficient to unity.

3. Result and Discussion

From this approach, it is interestingly observed that when j is absorbed into $\frac{\partial D}{\partial t}$, it is considered as zero and this enables us to obtain an expression in terms of conductivity from time independent electric field as shown in equation [20] that enable us obtain equation [21] that reveals the frequency dependent nature of dielectric function and conductivity of magnesium. From this relation, it is observed that at low frequency below the smallest frequency, ω_j , all the terms containing the sum with positive refractive index is related to the dielectric constant as given in equation [13]. One of the latent observation is the impact of the conductivity of the metal on the dielectric function which invariably has a contribution from bound electrons as in equation [22]. The skin depth which is related to the conductivity reveals the dependence of the attenuation characteristic of the material on the conductivity. Another interesting phenomenon is the variation of reflection coefficient with n and k at the plasma edge depending on relaxation region taken into consideration.

4. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have presented a number of properties which can be studied with the beam propagation when it comes to the properties of materials. It is observed that Maxwell's equations which were the primary mathematical tool present the enabling approach that made it possible to apply the expression that contains enough parameters required to describe the dielectric constant of magnesium as a metal and how it influences the optical properties and the influence of conductivity on the propagated wave through the material. This information allowed the understanding of how the dielectric constant variation influences the various properties such the refractive index and extinction coefficient.

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